

SLOPE STABILITY ANALYSIS UNDER DIFFERENT SOIL NAILING PARAMETERS USING SLIDE (ROCSCIENCE) SOFTWARE

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Abstract. To investigate the effects of different soil nailing parameters on the safety factor of a slope, a comprehensive analysis was conducted using the SLIDE (Rocscience) software and the bishop method. The analysis focused on parameters such as nail inclination, horizontal spacing, and length, which have been shown to impact the stability of slopes significantly. The results of the analysis indicate that the slope has the highest safety factor when soil nailing is inclined at an angle of approximately 10° to 20°. This means that soil nails installed at this angle provide the most effective reinforcement, enhancing the stability of the slope. the safety factor decreases with the increase of soil-nail horizontal spacing, and the safety factor increases with the increase soil nail length.

Introduction

Slope stabilization techniques are essential in controlling slope instability and preventing landslides. Soil stabilization is a process of modifying natural soil to meet specific engineering requirements through physical, chemical, and biological treatments. The slope stability is a critical factor that determines the safety of a slope, and it is calculated using the factor of safety (FOS). A FOS greater than 1.5 indicates that the resisting force due to the shear strength of the soil is higher than the driving force due to the self-weight of the sloping ground, and vice versa. When the factor of safety is less than 1.5, the slope is at risk of failure. To prevent slope failure, various slope stabilization techniques can be used, such as soil nailing.” “Soil nailing is a popular technique used in earth slopes to reinforce and strengthen the slope by using nails. The first soil nailing application was in 1972 in France, and it involved installing high-density grouted soil nails into the sloping ground. The technique has since been refined, and it involves drilling holes into the slope and then inserting steel bars or nails into the holes. The space around the nails is filled with grout, which helps to bond the nails with the surrounding soil. The nails act as tension members that reinforce the slope and increase the factor of safety of the soil slope.” “To better understand the effects of soil nailing on slope stability, a parametric study was conducted. The study investigated the impact of different factors such as nail inclination, nail spacing, and nail length on slope stability. The results of the study showed that soil nailing is an effective method of stabilizing slopes, and the nail inclination, spacing, and length have a significant impact on the factor of safety of the slope. Rocscience Slide v6 software was used to analyze the length, nail inclination, and soil properties affect the stability of soil-nailed slopes. The numerical model is validated through comparison with existing literature, and the findings slope failure, which is based on the theories and principles of the Limit Equilibrium Method (LEM).

Literature References

“Shivkumar Hallale, Syeda Sara, Mahesh Gite, Mayur Mohite⁴, Padamaja Shinde, Mohini Rengade (2023)”

“Slope failure is a natural occurrence that can pose a risk to human life and property. To prevent these risks, engineers need to design appropriate technical methods to stabilize slopes. In this study, we used GEO5 software to analyze natural slopes and identify the best soil stabilization technique. We found that soil nailing is a useful technique for stabilizing slopes by analyzing unstable slopes using GEO5 2017 software. Our paper includes case studies that illustrate the use of soil-nailing techniques for slope stabilization in different environmental conditions. We conclude that soil nailing is a promising method for slope stabilization that can mitigate the risks of slope failure. This paper provides valuable insights for researchers and engineers working in the field of slope stability analysis and soil stabilization.”

“Amr M. Rashad, Mostafa D. Hashem, Afaf Abdel Halim Mahmoud, Tarek Elsayed Mahmoud (2023)”

“Road embankments are prone to sudden failures, which makes it crucial to understand the mechanism of slope stability and optimize mathematical models to increase safety factors and identify slip surface positioning. In this study, we analyze the impact of soil nailing on the slope stability of road embankments under traffic load, using the optimized LEM. We examine the inclination, spacing, and length of soil nailing to provide valuable insights into the slope stability mechanism of road embankments. The mathematical analysis is conducted using SLOPE/W software, which enhances the results of the limit equilibrium method using an optimization function. Our study concludes that soil nailing reinforces slope stability and increases the value of the safety coefficient and slip surface modelling.”

“Tausif E Elahi, Md Azijul Islam, and Mohammad Shariful Islam (2022)”

“This paper presents a numerical method to evaluate the stability of slopes reinforced with soil nailing. The study aims to investigate how various parameters such as nail indicate that soil nailing can significantly enhance the stability of slopes. The research provides valuable insights into the optimal design of soil-nailed slopes and can be useful for engineers and researchers working in the field of geotechnical engineering.”

“Shanmugapriya Dewedree and Siti Norafida Jusoh (2019)”

“This paper discusses the use of soil nailing as a method to prevent slope failures. The study aims to determine the most effective values for stabilizing soil slopes using SLOPE/W software. Furthermore, the study evaluates the Factor of Safety (FOS) of a case study to validate the results. The paper concludes that soil nailing is an effective and economical system for slope stabilization.”

“Dildar Ali Mangnejo, S. J. Oad, Shahbaz Ali Kalhor, F. H. Laghari, Z. A. Siyal (2019)”

“This research paper discusses the use of numerical analysis to investigate the effectiveness of soil nailing techniques for stabilizing soil slopes. The study uses finite element method (FEM) software PLAXIS 2D to analyze the stability of a soil slope reinforced with soil nails under various loading

conditions. The results show that soil nailing is an effective method to improve soil slope stability and prevent slope failure. The study emphasizes the importance of appropriate design and installation of soil nails for optimal performance. The findings of this research can be useful for engineers and researchers working on slope stabilization projects.”

“Shamsan Alsubal, Indra S. H. Harahap and Nuraddeen Muhammad Babangida (2017)”

“This paper describes a typical design for stabilizing a soil slope using a soil nailing system. The design of soil nailing systems is influenced by various factors, including the inclination, spacing, and length of soil nails. The appropriate inclination of soil nails is achieved when the available bond length behind the slip surface is long enough for the bar to use its allowable load. The spacing between soil nails should be as wide as possible to achieve a Factor of Safety (FOS) of more than 1.3, which ensures compliance with design criteria and minimizes installation costs. The length of soil nails should be determined based on the soil properties, slope geometry, and design loads. Soil nailing is a cost-effective and efficient method for stabilizing soil slopes, and its design should be based on a thorough understanding of the site conditions and soil properties.”

“Surender Singh (2017)”

“This paper reports the findings of an experimental investigation into the behaviour of soil slopes that are unreinforced and soil-nailed under various static surcharge loads. The study examines the impact of different soil nail patterns within the soil slope. To conduct the study, a physical model of a soil slope was used, with and without soil nails. Soil nails made of aluminium hollow tubes were employed, with varying inclinations and arrangements. The study's results demonstrate that soil nailing is an effective method of stabilizing slopes, and the soil nail pattern has a significant effect on the slope's stability. The study concludes that soil nailing can be utilized to stabilize slopes in a range of soil conditions, and the soil nail pattern must be thoughtfully considered while designing a soil nailing system.”

“Ou-Ling Tang and Qing Ming – Jiang (2015)”

“This research paper presents a stability analysis of a slope using different soil nailing parameters, which were evaluated with the help of GeoStudio software and the Morgenstern Price method. The study is based on a slope located in the Beibei district of Chongqing province, where material parameters such as $\gamma = 18 \text{ kN/m}^3$, $c = 14 \text{ kPa}$, $\phi = 26^\circ$, and bond interface strength between soil nail and soil τ of 40 kPa were taken into consideration. The research analyzed the sensitivity of each soil-nailing parameter, including soil-nail dip angle, soil-nail horizontal space, soil-nail length, and soil-nail inclination angle. The results indicate that the safety factor of the slope increases with an increase in soil-nail dip angle but decreases with an increase in soil-nail horizontal space and soil-nail length. The optimal obliquity of soil nailing for achieving the highest safety factor is found to be around $30\text{-}40^\circ$. These findings can be useful for field engineers who are designing soil nailing systems.”

Methodology.

The study followed the methodology outlined below.

- ☐ Collection of soil samples for experimental investigation.
- ☐ Identify soil sample characteristics.
- ☐ Modelling and analysis of Slope using SLIDE software
- ☐ Identify the effect of the factor of safety (FOS) without Soil nailing.

- ☐ Evaluate the influence of nail length, nail spacing, and soil nail inclination.

Laboratory Test - Laboratory tests were conducted on the soil sample to determine its engineering properties by IS: 2720 provisions.

- ☐ Sieve Analysis.
- ☐ Natural Moisture Content.
- ☐ Specific Gravity.
- ☐ Atterberg Limit.
- ☐ Density Test.
- ☐ Triaxial test.

Table: Summary table of Soil test result (IS: 2720)

Property	Parameter	Test Value
Specific gravity	Specific gravity, GS	2.56
Grain size distribution	Particle size (%)	Silt = 50.53% Clay = 42.75%
Atterberg limits	Liquid limit, LL (%)	49.45%
	Plastic limit, PL (%)	24.04%
	Plasticity index, PI (%)	25.41%
Natural Moisture Content	Water Content (%)	14.29%
Shear strength parameters	Cohesion, c (kPa)	35
	Angle of internal friction	14
Soil classification	Unified soil classification system (USCS)	CI-CH
Unit weight	unit weight (Kn/m ³)	23 Kn/m ³

Modelling and Analysis – The article uses SLIDE V6 software to analyze the slope. SLIDE V6 The slope stability in clay was investigated at an angle of 700. Figure 5.1 shows the typical section of a slope in clay. The height and width of the slope is 10m.

Soil Material Properties - Based on the lab test results, the soil parameters have been considered.

Table: Soil Material Properties

Soil Classification	CI-CH
Density (kn/m ³)	23 kn/m ³
Cohesion (Kpa)	35
The angle of internal friction (degree) ϕ'	14

In this article, we need to analyze whether the slopes are stable or unstable using the SLIDE software.

Fig. Modelling analysis to determine the FOS of the slope

This article analyzes laboratory data assigned to a model for evaluating slope stability. The model's material properties were assigned, and the results revealed that the slope is weak, as indicated by a

factor of safety of 1.020, which is less than the recommended minimum of 1.5. Therefore, it is crucial to reinforce or stabilize the slope to ensure its safety and stability.

Result and Discussion.

For slope Analysis consider the following different parameters:

Height of slope	10m
The angle of the slope	70°
Diameter of soli nail	25mm
Length of soil nail	5m, 5.5m, 6m,6.5m, 7m, 7.5m, 8.00m & 8.50m
Spacing of soil nail	0.50m, 1.0m, 1.5m, 2.0m, 2.5m, 3.00m, 3.5m & 4.00m
Soil nail's inclination angle	5°, 10°, 15°, 20°, 25°, 30°, 35° & 40°

Consider the soil nail parameter with the help of a soil nailing design chart.

Table: The design parameters of soil nailing

Angle	15°
Length	6m
Spacing	1.5m

The Influence of Soil Nailing Parameters on the Safety Factor of Slope

1. **The influence of soil-nail angle** – The soil-nail angles are changed to 5°, 10°, 15°, 20°, 25°, 30°, 35° & 40° to examine the impact of soil-nail angle α on the safety factor. All other parameters stay the same as they are in Table 5.3. Fig. 6.1 indicates the relationship between the soil nail's angle and the safety factor.

Figure: The Safety factors under different soil-nails angles

As the soil-nail angle increases, the safety factor initially increases and eventually decreases, as shown in Figure

- The Influence of Soil-Nail Horizontal Spacing** - to examine the impact of soil-nail horizontal spacing on the safety factor, the spacing between soil particles is varied to a length of 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2, 2.5, 3, 3.5 & 4 meters. other parameters, however, stay the same as those listed in Table. Fig. shows the relationship between the horizontal soil nail spacing and the safety factor.

Figure: The Safety factors under different soil-nail horizontal spacing

As can be seen from Fig. The safety factor decreases with the increase of soil-nail horizontal spacing.

- The Influence of Soil-Nail Length** – In order to examine the impact of soil-nail length on the safety factor, the other parameters are kept constant at 5 m, 5.5 m, 6 m, 6.5 m, 7m, 7.5m, 8m and 8.5 m. Fig. 6.3 indicates the relationship between the soil nail's length and the safety factor.

Figure: The Safety factors under different soil-nail length

As can be seen from Fig. Increasing the soil-nail length to increase the stability of the slope.

Conclusion-

The stability of a soil slope with soil nailing is studied with Slide v6 software, and the conclusions are as follows:

1. As the soil-nail angle increases, the safety factor first increases and subsequently Decreases. Based on these measurements, we can determine that the soil nail angle needed to reinforce the slope is between 10° and 20°.
2. As the horizontal spacing between nails increases, the safety factor decreases. Based on these observations, we can determine that the optimal horizontal spacing between soil and nails is between 0.5 and 1.5 meters.
3. As soil nail length increases, it also increases the safety factor. For this slope, the optimum soil nail length is between 6 to 7 meters.
4. Changes in the length, angle, and spacing of soil nails are all influenced by the safety factor.

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